

THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE THINKING AND METHODS OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *In this article, the importance of creative thinking, its benefits in the student's life and studies and recommendations for teachers to use were explained. Furthermore, the main aim of this article is to examine the impact of creative thinking development on improving speaking skills, creative approach to problem solving and expression ideas of students.*

Keywords: *creativity, optimal solution, education, method, appropriation, pedagogical skill, opinion, innovation.*

Creativity encourages us to continue learning new things while allowing us to process information in a different way. Research shows that creativity keeps our minds sharp and young. It helps us process information in ways that help us find unusual solutions to problems. We should always remember that a creative mind is a thriving mind!

Creativity is one of the skills that are important for a person to have in his work and life today. Creative thinking encourages us to solve any problems, find exclusive answers to them and even make discoveries. If we look into the past, many famous and successful people have lived until now. Why were they successful? Because they have these abilities, they created inventions that are difficult for mankind to imagine. From this we can know that creative thinking is one of the main tools on the way to success. We cannot even imagine a day without electricity, cars, computers, the Internet and telephones, and we can give many examples of such inventions. It is not a secret to all of us that their inventions made a great contribution to the rapid development of the world and served to facilitate the living conditions of people, making it easier for us to live today. From the point of view of the present time, it seems that all the necessary and necessary things have already been created, and nothing new can be done now. But in fact, it is not like that, the human mind has no limits, and there are many issues that need to be solved in our current life. We definitely need young people who can think creatively and find the perfect solution in a short time. President Sh.Mirziyoyev said: "In order for our youth to become independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field in the world, our state and the words "we will mobilise all the forces and possibilities of our society" are proof that this topic is relevant. Despite the fact that creativity is one of the most difficult abilities to acquire, we must not forget that the greatest responsibility for its formation lies with pedagogues. Only if the teacher himself has the qualities of creativity, can he encourage students to develop this ability.

Various methods can be used to develop such skills in students. Including:

1. Encourage them to think outside their shell

At the same time, the teacher should ask the students interesting questions that they have not encountered before, and also ask their opinions on the situations that are important in the present time. Because the students' brains are used to common, simple questions every day, and the range of thinking has not yet expanded. It is necessary to gradually increase the complexity of

the questions from the easy level. If they cannot find an answer to more complex questions, the teacher should justify and fully explain the answer to the question. By conducting this activity every day, but for a short time, it is ensured that students do not get bored. In this way, their worldviews begin to expand and they adapt to thinking about today's problems in extracurricular situations.

2. Allow students to make mistakes

During the debate on the topic, even if the student expresses a wrong opinion, listen to the speech until the end, without interrupting his opinion. It is appropriate to explain the correct answer and explain where the mistake was made, rather than punishing him for making a mistake. As a result of hearing reprimands from his peers while the student is answering, his psyche is hurt, he may even stop thinking in the next debates. The possibilities of the mind must be explained by teaching not to be afraid to make mistakes, to take risks, and that this is natural. Inculcating that a person who does not make mistakes is actually a person who does nothing, and proving it through the lives of great people, forms the concept that nothing is impossible for them. Without failure, there is no innovation and creativity (Brian Brown).

3. Using interactive games appropriate to the topic in the lesson

The ability to interest students is one of the most important factors in the effective organisation of the lesson. Through interest in science, students can achieve many good results and successes. For this, the teacher can start each new lesson in an interesting way, using different methods for a new topic during the lesson. Using games to reinforce a subject is always the best option in any classroom. Because the game can attract schoolchildren of any age.

4. Using technology in every lesson

Technology is everywhere. Technology is the best way to engage students. It ensures that the lesson is interesting and understandable. Most importantly, the use of various innovative technologies gives them many opportunities to improve their outlook and achieve success.

5. Encourage students to learn a new language

Learning languages expands children's brainpower and thinking. Knowing more than one language helps students to multitask, to concentrate for a long time, to solve problems faster and to approach them in a different way. According to research, children who know languages have several advantages over their peers in other subjects. In addition, the best way to strengthen memory is to learn a language.

6. Set aside time for creative work

Allowing you to independently complete projects and provide solutions at the end of each day or week. In this case, the teacher gives one task to students individually or in groups. And they puzzle over that task for the specified time and try to find its optimal solution. It is natural that each student or group performs the task in a different way and finds different solutions. As Albert Einstein said: "Creativity is seeing what others see and thinking what no one else has." they will get more information and, in addition, they will develop team-working skills.

7. Encouragement.

Incentives serve as motivation for students. Every word that the teacher praises them strengthens their self-confidence and thus they can break the boundaries of thought. Through this, students' interest develops, their activity in the lesson increases, and the relationship between the teacher and the student improves.

Creativity is a healthy self-esteem booster, as it allows us to be more confident in ourselves and our abilities through the art of discovery. We explore possibilities that would have otherwise been impossible or impractical. We see the world in differently, and then share it with others through the creation of new ideas, works of art, music, dance, literature...the list goes on! Creativity helps you understand other people's perspectives. It sees through new eyes and different lenses. This allows us to create solutions that may not have been attempted before. Creativity also allows for new ideas and understanding of the problems we face. It helps us look at things from different angles, giving us a better chance to be fair, original and smart when it comes to negotiating with people whether it's finding a solution or mediating a conflict.

From what has been discussed and analysed above it can be inferred that it should be noted that the present time and situation require creativity. Because this ability helps people avoid uniformity and look at any problem with a different perspective. Since the development of our country and its bright future are in the hands of young people, education of well-rounded and well-educated individuals is the most important goal of our country.

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